

Hyperfine Interactions in the Mixed Ligand Complexes of Iron Thioglycolate with some Amines

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Mössbauer studies on the ferric polyamino carboxylate¹, ferric squarate² and complexes of the type³ FeL_4X_2 (L = heterocyclic amines and X = halide or thiocyanate ions) have established the correlation between isomer shift, quadrupole splitting and molecular structure. A large number of iron thioglycollate complexes have also been reported⁴. The present study deals with the preparation and characterisation of complexes formed by the interaction of some amines with sodium bis(thioglycolato)diaquoferrate(III).

Results and discussion

The solutions of complexes 1 and 2 (Table 1) in acetonitrile and of others in water gave the values of molar conductance in the range 88–95 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ indicating thereby the presence of two ions. The room temperature magnetic moment values of all the complexes were ≈ 5.82 B.M., a characteristic of high-spin Fe^{III} . The electronic spectra of the complexes gave three bands at 20 000 ($\epsilon \approx 10$), 33 000 ($\epsilon \approx 50$) and 40 000 ($\epsilon \approx 1000$) cm^{-1} corresponding to transitions ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ respectively⁵.

The ir bands observed at 1 650 (C=O), 1 410 (C–O) and 1 240 cm^{-1} (C–O, O–C=O) in the free ligand (thioglycollic acid) shifted to 1 580, 1 390 and 1 150 cm^{-1} respectively, in the complexes, indicating the involvement of carboxyl group in coordination. The band at 2 460 cm^{-1} (S–H) disappeared in the spectra of the complexes. The bands at 450, 550 and 600 cm^{-1} in the spectra of complexes were assignable to M–S, M–N and M–O stretching vibrations respectively. The complexes 1, 4 and 6 gave three extra bands at 3 350, 845 and 670 cm^{-1} which may be due to the presence of water inside the coordination sphere or NH. The bands due to C=C and C=N stretching of the heterocyclic

amines shifted from 1 500 and 1 600 cm^{-1} to 1 515 and 1 620 cm^{-1} respectively, in the complexes, indicating coordination through a nitrogen atom or atoms.

Least-square fitted Mössbauer parameters are presented in Table 1. The room temperature Mössbauer spectra exhibited a broad (0.6 mm/s) and assymmetric doublet which persists down to 80 K and whose line width increased by about 20 percent with reduction in temperature. The persistence of assymmetric intensities was suggestive of the Goldanskii-Kayagin effect⁶. The quadrupole doublet collapsed into a broad singlet at 50 K with further increase in line width. All this is indicative of relaxation taking place. There was no appreciable temperature-dependence of isomer shift and quadrupole splitting. Thioglycolate combining with other ligands could give rise to isomers which could account for the large line widths. However, the spectrum could not be resolved satisfactorily into multiple doublets. The values of isomer shift and quadrupole splitting and their temperature-independence indicated the presence of iron in the +3 state with high-spin distorted octahedral symmetry which may be due to the presence of different types of ligands in the coordination sphere. The values of numbers of unpaired electrons may be due to the donation of electrons from metal orbitals towards the ligand orbitals. This would also explain the slightly higher values of isomer shifts.

The thermal analysis indicated the removal of two water molecules from complex 1 at about 250° and one water molecule from complex 4 at about 210°, confirming the presence of these water molecules inside the coordination sphere.

Experimental

Freshly prepared solutions of the amines, sodium thioglycolate, sodium hydroxide and ferric chloride

TABLE 1 - MOSSBAUER PARAMETERS AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd no	Complexes Compd */(yield %)	I S mm/s	Q S mm/s	Analysis % Found/(Calcd)		
				Fe	C	H
1	Na[Fe(C ₂ H ₂ O ₂ S) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂] (75)	—	—	19.16 (18.98)	16.15 (16.27)	2.73 (2.71)
2	Na[Fe(C ₂ H ₂ O ₂ S) ₂ (C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂)] (65)	0.33	0.72	12.88 (12.75)	43.22 (43.73)	2.75 (2.73)
3	Na[Fe(C ₂ H ₂ O ₂ S) ₂ (C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂)] (65)	0.31	0.63	13.62 (13.49)	40.09 (40.48)	2.91 (2.89)
4	Na[Fe(C ₂ H ₂ O ₂ S) ₂ (C ₄ H ₉ NO)(H ₂ O)] (60)	0.18	0.36	15.52 (15.38)	26.13 (26.37)	4.15 (4.12)
5	Na[Fe(C ₂ H ₂ O ₂ S) ₂ (C ₆ H ₇ N) ₂] (60)	0.18	0.37	15.43 (15.30)	32.49 (32.78)	3.02 (3.00)
6	Na[Fe(C ₂ H ₂ O ₂ S) ₂ (C ₆ H ₁₈ N ₄)] (70)	0.31	0.62	13.95 (13.82)	29.47 (29.62)	5.48 (5.43)

*C₂H₂O₂S = thioglycolate C₁₂H₈N₂ = o-phenanthroline C₁₀H₈N₂ = 2,2'-bipyridyl C₄H₉NO = morpholine C₆H₇N = γ -picoline C₆H₁₈N₄ = triethylenetetraamine

(A R B D H) in distilled water were used

Iron thioglycollate was prepared by mixing 0.05 M aqueous solutions of ferric chloride and sodium thioglycollate in the molar ratio of 1 : 2. The precipitates formed were filtered, washed with water and dried in the desiccator over anhydrous sulphuric acid. The iron thioglycollate and the secondary ligand complexes (γ -picoline, triethylenetetraamine, morpholine, o-phenanthroline and 2,2'-bipyridyl) were prepared by refluxing equimolar proportions in absolute alcohol. Brownish orange coloured precipitates formed were washed with the solvent and then dried in a vacuum desiccator. The analytical and molar conductance values are given in Table 1.

IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Beckman IR-20 spectrometer, electronic spectra on a DU-6 UV-VIS spectrophotometer. Mossbauer spectra on a constant acceleration type spectrometer using Co⁵⁷(Rh) source. 512 channels of MCA were used to store the spectra. Velocity calibration was done using a thin iron foil and reflectance spectra on a Carl-Zeiss SPECOL spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility was measured on a vibrating sample magnetometer (Princeton Applied Research) in the temperature range of 300–77 K.

Thermal studies were done on a Stanton Redcraft TG 770 and Fisher differential thermoanalyser 260 P 544

at a heating rate of 8°/min and chart speed 6"/h in a platinum crucible in an atmosphere of dry air using anhydrous alumina as a reference material. Metal analysis was done by an atomic absorption technique.

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